

EXAMPLES OF CANONIZATION AND DETERMINATION OF THE TYPE OF SECOND ORDER CURVES AND THEIR DIFFERENT SOLUTIONS

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Abstract. The given article presents different recommendations and methods for canonization of quadratic curves, as well as examples of their solution.

Keywords: second-order curve, canonical representation, ellipse, hyperbola, parabola, intersecting lines, parallel lines, invariant, simplification.

Simplification of general equations

$$a_{11}x^2 + 2a_{12}xy + a_{22}y^2 + 2a_{13}x + 2a_{23}y + a_{33} = 0 \quad (1)$$

It is important to suggest that the given study is concerned with determining the type of the second-order line given by the general equation (1) and making it canonic. We will also first get acquainted with the second-order line itself.

Definition: the lines defined by quadratic equations with respect to the variables x and y are called quadratic lines. Second-order lines play an important role in architecture, astronomy, mechanics and other branches of science and technology. Second-order lines can be divided into three groups:

- 1) Second-order lines with one center of symmetry
- 2) This group includes second-order lines without a center of symmetry.
- 3) The third group includes lines whose center of symmetry is a straight line. $x^2 + y^2 = r^2(0:0)$, The second-order line given by the equation is a circle of radius r with center at the point $(0:0)$, $\frac{x^2}{a^2} + \frac{y^2}{b^2} = 1$ an ellipse whose center is at the origin, $\frac{x^2}{a^2} - \frac{y^2}{b^2} = 1$ hyperbola given by the equation, $y^2 = 2px$ defines a parabola.

Let a general equation of the second degree with two variables be given:

$$a_{11}x^2 + 2a_{12}xy + a_{22}y^2 + 2a_{13}x + 2a_{23}y + a_{33} = 0 \quad (1)$$

In the above equation, a_{11} and a_{22} cannot be equal to zero simultaneously. It is clear from the given information that the canonical equations of the second-order curves considered above are eigenvalues of equation (1).

If $a_{11}=1, a_{12}=0, a_{22}=1, a_{13}=0, a_{23}=0, a_{33}=-r^2$ (1) equation $x^2 + y^2 = r^2$ takes the form, that is, this equation defines a circle.

$a_{11} = \frac{1}{a^2}, a_{12} = 0, a_{22} = \frac{1}{b^2}, a_{13}=0, a_{23}=0, a_{33}=-1$ (1) equation $\frac{x^2}{a^2} + \frac{y^2}{b^2} = 1$ defines the ellipse.

In $a_{11} = \frac{1}{a^2}, a_{12} = 0, a_{22} = -\frac{1}{b^2}, a_{13}=0, a_{23}=0, a_{33}=-1$ (1) equation

$\frac{x^2}{a^2} - \frac{y^2}{b^2} = 1$ defines the hyperbole.

$a_{11} = 0, a_{12} = 0, a_{22} = 1, a_{13} = -p, a_{23} = 0, a_{33} = 0$ (1) equation $y^2 = 2px$ will have the form, and therefore the equation of a parabola.

The following suggestion can be drawn from the above substitutions: therefore, an arbitrary second-order curve, given in general form, can be reduced to a canonical form. When we mean reducing a second-order line, given by a general equation, to a canonical state. If in the system of equations (1) a second-order curve is given in the coordinate system R, then, by rotating the coordinate system by an angle, we can go to a rectangular coordinate system R. If there is $a_{12} \neq 0$ in the equation (1), then we construct the characteristic equation of the line $\lambda^2 - (a_{11} + a_{22})\lambda + a_{11}a_{22} - a_{12}^2$ and find its roots λ_1, λ_2 according to the formula $\sin \alpha = \frac{\text{tg } \alpha_1}{\sqrt{1 + \text{tg}^2 \alpha_1}}, \cos \alpha = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \text{tg}^2 \alpha_1}}$, calculate $\text{tg } \alpha = \frac{\lambda_1 - a_{11}}{a_{12}}$. Taking into account the above, the coordinate vectors i', j' of the standard (o, i', j') are determined, created by rotating the coordinate system by an angle α .

$$i' = i \cos \alpha + j \sin \alpha \quad j' = j \cos \alpha - i \sin \alpha$$

Line equation in new rapter looks like this

$$\lambda_1 x'^2 + \lambda_2 y'^2 + 2a'_{13}x' + 2a'_{23}y' + a_{33} = 0$$

and the coefficients a'_{13}, a'_{23} are determined by the following formulas:

$$a'_{13} = a_{13} \cos \alpha + a_{23} \sin \alpha, \quad a'_{23} = a_{23} \cos \alpha - a_{13} \sin \alpha.$$

Taking into consideration all of these let us get acquainted with the next method of canonization of second-order strings, this method is called the "invariant" method.

$$I_1 = a_{11} + a_{22} \quad (1)$$

$$I_2 = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} \end{vmatrix} \quad (2)$$

$$K_3 = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} \end{vmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Definitely, the expressions we mentioned above are called invariants of lines of the second order with respect to the change of a rectangular coordinate system to another coordinate system, and the expressions $a_{12} = a_{21}, a_{31} = a_{13}, a_{32} = a_{23}$ are always appropriate here.

Let us determine the type and canonical equation of the second-order line according to the above invariants. We will give the characteristic equation for the specified invariants and determine the type of line according to the equation.

$\lambda^2 - I_1\lambda + I_2 = 0$, the roots λ_1 and λ_2 of this equation consist of real numbers. The lines of the second order can be divided into three groups, as we said above. The first group includes lines with a single center of symmetry, an ellipse, an abstract ellipse, two intersecting abstract lines, a hyperbole, and two intersecting real lines. $I_2 \neq 0$ necessary and sufficient for a line of the second order to have a single center.

The second group includes lines that do not have a center of symmetry, i.e. a parabole. For a line to be a parabole, it is necessary and sufficient that $I_2 = 0, K_3 \neq 0$. The third group includes lines whose centers of symmetry form a straight line, two parallel lines, or two overlapping lines. In order for the centers of symmetry of a second-order line to form a straight line, it is necessary and sufficient that the condition $I_2 = 0, K_3 = 0$ can be met. The equation of the lines of the first group, formed by changing the rectangular coordinate system, is $\lambda_1 x^2 + \lambda_2 y^2 + \frac{K_3}{I_2} = 0$.

Moreover, the equation of the second group: $I_1 y^2 \pm 2 \sqrt{-\frac{K_3}{I_1}} x = 0$. We can reduce the equation of the third group to the form $I_1 x^2 + \frac{K_2}{I_1} = 0$. The necessary and sufficient conditions for the membership of second-order lines in the specified groups are expressed by the relations between their invariants as follows:

I. It is an ellipse if the conditions $I_2 > 0$, $I_1, K_3 < 00$ are met, an abstract ellipse is $I_2 > 0$, $I_1, K_3 > 0$. Two intersecting abstract lines $I_2 > 0$, $K_3 = 0$

Hyperbole $I_2 < 0$, $K_3 \neq 0$

II. Parabole $I_2 = 0$, $K_3 \neq 0$

III. Two parallel lines $I_2 = 0$, $K_3 = 0$, $K_2 > 0$

The straight line is blocked $I_2 = 0$, $K_3 = 0$, $K_2 = 0$. Now let us make the following example canonical by the method of invariants;

$$x^2 - 4xy + 4y^2 - 6x + 8y - 6 = 0$$

Solution: $a_{11} = 1, a_{22} = 4, a_{12} = a_{21} = -2, a_{13} = a_{31} = -3,$

$$a_{23} = a_{32} = 4, a_{33} = -6, I_1 = a_{11} + a_{22} = 1 + 4 = 5$$

$$I_2 = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & -2 \\ -2 & 4 \end{vmatrix} = 4 - 4 = 0$$

$$K_3 = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & -2 & -3 \\ -2 & 4 & 4 \\ -3 & 4 & -6 \end{vmatrix} = -24 + 24 + 24 - 36 + 24 - 16 = -4$$

By summerising it can be suggested that since $I_2 = 0$, $K_3 \neq 0$ the equation of a parabole, we will now bring this equation to the canonical state.

$$I_1 y^2 \pm 2 \sqrt{-\frac{K_3}{I_1}} x = 0; \leftrightarrow 5y^2 \pm 2 \sqrt{-\frac{-4}{5}} x = 0$$

$5y^2 - \frac{4}{\sqrt{5}} x = 0 \leftrightarrow y^2 = \frac{4}{5\sqrt{5}} x$ has the same canonical form as the equation above.

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